

An Alternative Synthesis of Chloroquine Diol

A. K. Sen

The effectiveness of chloroquine mustard and a related few other compounds against some human neoplasms has been established¹. The synthesis of isotopically labelled chloroquine mustard for some biological studies led us to search for an alternative short-step synthesis.

Carmack *et al.*² prepared 4-aminopentan-1-ol in 74-80% yield by catalytic hydrogenation of 1-hydroxypentan-4-one oxime in presence of Raney nickel. Duplication of the above procedure using Raney Ni-W2 left a wholly carbonised residue. It has now been found that by using ethanolic ammonia as a solvent, the oxime could be reduced in 94% yield. The oily mixed sulphate and hydrobromide salt of 7-chloro-4-(4-bromo-1-methylbutylamino)quinoline, prepared essentially according to the procedure described by Carmack *et al.*², was allowed to react with excess of diethanolamine in acetone to furnish the required chloroquine diol in 30% yield.

4-Aminopentan-1-ol.—A mixture of 1-hydroxypentan-4-one oxime (29g., 0.33M), Raney Ni-W2 (3 g.), and ethanolic ammonia (5%, 40 ml) was hydrogenated at an initial pressure of 1600 lb./in². The temperature was slowly raised during 4 hr. to 70°; during the period the consumption of hydrogen was completed. The catalyst was filtered, the solvent removed, and the residue distilled under reduced pressure; b.p. 105-107°/11-12mm, yield 94%.

7-Chloro-4-[4-bis-(β-hydroxyethyl)amino-1-methylbutylamino]quinoline (Chloroquine Diol).—To the oily mixed salt of 7-chloro-4-(4-bromo-1-methylbutylamino)quinoline, prepared from a sample 7-chloro-4-(4-hydroxy-1-methylbutylamino)quinoline (5.3 g.) essentially according to Carmack *et al.*², was added a mixture of diethanolamine (15 g.) and the reagent grade acetone (25 ml). The initial turbid and two-phase mixture became clear and uniform on shaking for 2 min. After keeping for 4 days at the room temperature, the solution was gently refluxed on a steam cone for 3 hr. and the solvent removed. A mixture of acetic acid (10 ml) and water (20 ml) was added, cooled, ammonia added to just turbidity (pH 7-8), and extracted with ether (25 ml × 3). The aqueous portion was then made strongly ammoniacal and extracted portionwise with chloroform (40 ml × 1 and 25 ml × 2). The combined chloroform extract was washed with ammonium acetate solution and dried with potassium carbonate. On removing the solvent, the diol was obtained as a brown oil (3.2 g.). The oil was induced to crystallise from ethyl acetate, yielding (30%)

1. Jones *et al.*, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1958, **66**, 1113.
2. J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1946, **68**, 1220.

a white crystalline solid. On recrystallisation from ethylene dichloride, the product melted at 120-24° and was identical with chloroquine diol, obtained from the original procedure of Jones *et al.*³.

The author expresses his sincere thanks to Dr. C. C. Price, Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Pennsylvania, U.S.A., for providing necessary facilities and for his interest in the work.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY,
Kharagpur.

Received March 15, 1965.